

Organic fluids near a hard wall : Statistical mechanical approach

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The surface free energies along with the adsorption of some organic compounds like formamide, acetonitrile, dimethyl formamide, acetone, 1,2-dichloroethane, 1,1-dichloroethane and normal chain alcohols ($n = 1-5$), assuming as hard sphere fluids, at a planar wall have been calculated using a density functional theory (DFT). The behavior of liquids at solid-liquid interface has been discussed. The results differ from that of scale particle theory due to inhomogeneity of the fluid near the surface.

The inhomogeneity of the density of the fluids near a interface can be studied by the density functional theory (DFT)^{1,2}. In this approach the grand potential is expressed as a functional of the non-uniform density distribution. The minimization of this functional with respect to the change in density distribution leads to the free energy and profile of density. Density functional theory can be modified with weighted density approximation² which can be applied to a wide variety of fluids including polymers³. Simplest model of the interface is the one with solid as smooth hard wall and the liquid as the simple hard sphere fluid. The real interface are more complex one and the method can be improved by including the wall-wall, wall-fluid and fluid-fluid interactions^{4,5}. The surface tension and adsorption of some hard sphere fluids, near hard flat wall can be calculated from Attard's⁴ density functional method with Carnahan-Starling's equation of state.

The results obtained for surface free energies along with the adsorption of some organic compounds (viz. formamide, acetonitrile, dimethyl formamide, acetone, 1,2-dichloroethane and normal chain alcohols, $n = 1-5$) at a planar wall by DFT are compared with scale particle theory (SPT) to study the inhomogeneity effect on the physical properties.

Theory and calculations :

According to the DFT of Attard⁴ the surface grand potential $\Omega_s(\rho)$ can be written as

$$\Omega_s(\rho) = \Omega + PV \quad (1)$$

where, Ω is grand potential; P , V are the pressure and volume respectively. The equilibrium density profile of the inhomogeneous fluid corresponds to the minimum of the grand potential, which satisfies

$$\frac{\delta\Omega(\rho)}{\delta\rho(r)} = 0$$

where, $\rho(r)$ is the single particle density. For surfaces,

$$\frac{\delta\Omega(s)}{\delta\mu} = -\int dz[\rho(z) - \rho] \quad (2)$$

where, A is the area of the inhomogeneity, ρ the bulk fluid density, and $\rho(z)$ the fluid density at z .

So the knowledge of density profile can determine the equilibrium properties of a inhomogeneous system. We consider a system or subsystem possessing an unidirectional inhomogeneity oriented perpendicular to z -axis. The rectangular subsystem obtained by inserting walls which do not affect in any way the states of the neighbouring fluids and then moving one of the walls that lie parallel to z -axis, i.e. move the yz -boundary along the x -axis. This process introduces a complete fraction α .

According to statistical mechanics the change in the grand potential,

$$\Delta\Omega = \alpha\Omega \quad (3)$$

According to the second law of thermodynamics. $\Delta\Omega$ is the work done on the subsystem and this is equal to $-\alpha A \int dz P_T(z)$ and so

$$\Omega = A \int dz P_T(z) \quad (4)$$

where, $P_T(z)$ is the tranverse pressure tensor. The zeroth moment of $P_T(z)$ is known. Combining eqns. (3) and (4),

$$\Omega = -A \int_0^\infty dz [P - P(z)]$$

In the case of fluid interface between fluid and hard wall the intermolecular potential energy,

$$V = V_{\text{hard wall}} \text{ and } V_{\text{HW}} = \infty \text{ when } Z < 0 \\ = 0 \text{ when } Z > 0$$

The adsorption value can be determined from the equation,

$$\Gamma = \int_0^\infty dz [P - P(z)] \quad (5)$$

$$\text{and } -\frac{\delta\gamma}{\delta\mu} = \Gamma \quad (6)$$

The SPT relates the equilibrium properties of bulk fluids with the change in the grand potential on the insertion of a hard particle

Now the Carnahan-Starling equation of state,

$$\frac{P_{CS}}{\rho kT} = \frac{1 + \eta + \eta^2 + \eta^3}{(1 - \eta)^3} \quad (7)$$

and that of scaled particle theory,

$$\frac{P_{SPT}}{\rho kT} = \frac{1 + \eta + \eta^2}{(1 - \eta)^3} \quad (8)$$

where, P is the pressure, ρ the bulk density, T the absolute temperature, k the Boltzman constant and η the packing fraction = $1/6 \pi \rho \sigma^3$, where σ is the hard-sphere diameter

Attard⁸ used the Force-Balance Monte Carlo Computer simulation technique to calculate the excess chemical potential for different $\rho\sigma^3$. The simulation results show that there is good agreements between this result and the Carnahan-Starling equation of state

According to Reiss *et al*⁶, the surface tension of a fluid a near a hard wall is

$$-4\pi\beta\gamma\sigma^2 = 12\eta \left(\frac{\beta p}{\rho} \right) - \frac{6\eta(2 + \eta)}{(1 - \eta)^2}, \eta = \frac{\pi}{6} \rho\sigma^3 \quad (9)$$

Combining (8) and (9),

$$-\beta\gamma\sigma^2 = \frac{9\eta^2(1 + \eta)}{2\pi(1 - \eta)^3} \quad (10)$$

From this we can calculate $-\frac{d\gamma}{d\mu}$

With SPT equation of state we get,

$$\Gamma_{SPT} \sigma^2 = \frac{9\eta^2}{\pi(1 + 2\eta)} \quad (11)$$

and with CS equation of state,

$$\beta P \sigma^3 = \frac{6\eta(1 + \eta + \eta^2 + \eta^3)}{(1 - \eta)^3} \quad (12)$$

$$\text{and } \Gamma_{CS} = \Gamma_{SPT} [1 - (4\eta^3 - \eta^4)(1 + 2\eta)^{-2}]^{-1} \quad (13)$$

From eqns (11) and (13), Γ_{SPT} and Γ_{CS} can be calculated. The values of exact Γ can be compared with the Monte Carlo results

Results and Discussion

The hard sphere diameter (σ) of some organic compounds and the corresponding packing fractions (η) are given in Table 1. The packing fraction (η) varied from $\eta = 0.358$ to 0.568 which corresponds to the liquid range. Fig 1 shows the variation of $\beta\gamma\sigma^2$ with η . The surface tensions

Fig. 1. Variation of surface free energies with packing density for some organic fluids at a planar wall

calculated according to SPT (i.e. eqn 10) and $\beta\gamma\sigma^2$ represents that obtained from eqn (9). From Fig 1 it may be noted that thermodynamic and mechanical routes to the surface tension are consistent within statistical error.

Table 1 Fluid parameters

Compd	σ Å	η
Water ^a	2.76	0.365
Methanol ^b	3.59	0.358
Ethanol ^b	4.36	0.445
Propanol ^b	4.71	0.439
Butanol ^b	5.45	0.557
Pentanol ^b	5.80	0.568
Formamide ^a	3.63	0.378
Acetonitrile ^a	4.12	0.417
Dimethyl formamide ^a	4.98	0.503
Acetone ^a	4.86	0.489
1,2-Dichloroethane ^a	5.08	0.520
1,1-Dichloroethane ^a	5.07	0.485

^aCalculated from Ref 8 ^bCalculated from Ref 9

At low density region, eqns (9) and (10) tend to the same result upto order η^4 ,

$$-\beta\gamma\sigma^2 = \frac{9\eta^2(1 + 4\eta + 9\eta^2 + \dots)}{2\pi} \quad (14)$$

but at high density region there is an appreciable difference between the two results

We have also calculated the adsorptions $\Gamma_{SPT} \sigma^2$ and

$\Gamma_{CS} \sigma^2$ from eqns. (11) and (13), respectively, for these fluids at different packing fractions. The curves in Fig. 2 show the variation of $\Gamma_{SPT} \sigma^2$ and $\Gamma_{CS} \sigma^2$ against η for these compounds. This shows that Γ_{CS} has always higher values than Γ_{SPT} although both are smooth density dependent. At low density Γ_{SPT} is very close to Γ_{CS} but at high density region the difference is appreciable. The simulation

Fig. 2. Variation of $\Gamma\sigma^2$ with packing density (η) for some organic compounds on a planar wall

data are taken from Henderson⁷ and compared with Γ_{SPT} and Γ_{CS} . The comparison is shown in Fig. 2 (the circles are simulation results). It shows that best fit to the Monte Carlo results is given by the equation,

$$\Gamma_{\text{exact}} = 0.33 \Gamma_{CS} + 0.66 \Gamma_{SPT} \quad (15)$$

The curves in Figs 1 and 2 show not only the variation of surface free energies and adsorptions against packing fractions, but implies that the surface free energies and adsorption for any hard sphere fluids whose packing densities fall within the range 0.35–0.59, can be determined. The calculated results are given in Table 2. The accuracy of the predicted results depends on the choice of hard sphere

diameter of the fluid as the packing force η is very sensitive to the choice of hard sphere diameter of the fluid

Table 2 Calculated surface free energies and adsorptions for different packing fractions

η	$-\beta\sigma^2\gamma_{SPT}$	$-\beta\sigma^2\gamma$	$\Gamma_{SPT}\sigma^2$	$\Gamma_{CS}\sigma^2$	$\Gamma_{\text{exact}}\sigma^2$
0.365	0.992	0.989	0.220	0.233	0.223
0.358	0.918	0.917	0.214	0.226	0.217
0.445	2.302	2.203	0.300	0.328	0.308
0.439	2.061	2.002	0.294	0.321	0.301
0.557	7.443	6.580	0.420	0.484	0.439
0.568	8.362	7.230	0.432	0.501	0.453
0.378	1.141	1.112	0.233	0.248	0.237
0.417	1.721	1.667	0.271	0.293	0.277
0.503	4.452	3.781	0.361	0.405	0.374
0.489	3.630	2.802	0.346	0.386	0.358
0.520	5.022	4.689	0.380	0.430	0.395
0.485	3.490	2.869	0.342	0.381	0.353

Variation of few percent in this diameter can cause a significant errors in the predicted results.

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